

PERCEIVED BENEFITS OF PARTICIPATION IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES ON STUDENTS' STRESS COPING

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the perceived benefits of participation in Physical Education classes for students' stress-coping, aiming to provide insights to improve educational policies and curriculum design. It sought to determine how PE participation contributes to students' ability to manage stress and enhance their physical, mental, and social well-being. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, involving 301 college students selected through stratified random sampling from eight departments of the University of La Salette, Santiago City, Philippines. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire on perceived benefits of Physical Education and Stress Levels. Statistical tools, including frequency and percentage distributions, weighted means, and SPSS, were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that students perceived PE classes as highly beneficial for reducing stress, improving mental health and social interaction, and enhancing academic performance. However, 82.4% of the respondents experienced high stress levels, highlighting the need for stronger wellness interventions. The study recommends implementing the "Move for a Change: Physical Education for Stress Management" program, which promotes mindfulness activities, active breaks, and student-led fitness challenges to normalize movement as a coping strategy. In conclusion, Physical Education plays a vital role in promoting holistic development and stress resilience among students. Institutions are encouraged to enhance PE programs, ensure inclusivity, and collaborate with guidance and student services to support overall well-being.

Keywords: *Perceived Benefits of Physical Education, Students' Stress Coping, Mental Health*

INTRODUCTION

Physical education classes have long been recognized as a vital component of a well-rounded academic curriculum, promoting not only physical fitness but also mental and emotional well-being (Bailey, 2020). In today's learning environment, where students juggle increasing academic demands, social expectations, and constant digital engagement, stress has become an ever-present challenge (American Psychological Association, 2020). Physical Education is perceived to contribute to improved focus, attentiveness, and learning engagement. These findings are supported by Teuber et al. (2024)

Recent studies highlight that physical activity can be a powerful coping strategy for helping students manage stress by improving mood and reducing stress, boosting self-esteem, and building resilience (Teuber et al., 2024). However, while the link between physical activity and mental well-being has been widely explored, the specific benefits of structured PE classes in supporting students' stress coping have received less attention.

Stress among students can stem from various sources, including academic workload, peer pressure, family expectations, and social interactions. If not effectively managed, chronic stress can lead to adverse psychological outcomes such as anxiety, depression, and burnout (Liu et al., 2025). Engaging in physical activity during PE classes provides students with an outlet to relieve tension, interact socially, and adopt healthy habits that contribute to overall well-being (Reigal et al., 2020). A 2025 study of Filipino senior high school students found that regular participation in PE was associated with lower academic stress, with intrinsic motivation as a significant factor (An, 2025). Despite these known benefits, the extent to which students perceive PE as helpful in managing their stress warrants further exploration.

Likewise, the Stress and Coping Theory suggests that physical activity is an adaptive strategy that helps individuals respond to and reduce stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 2020). Recent findings further support these ideas, indicating that PE participation can improve mental health indirectly by promoting social support and encouraging consistent exercise habits (Dishman et al., 2020). Although these perspectives provide a strong basis for understanding the benefits of physical activity, research specifically focused on the unique contributions of PE classes to stress reduction remains limited. These findings highlighted the central role of mental health- focused PE activities in addressing student stress. It supports the findings of Dinas et al. (2020) and Lee & Kim (2021) that structured PE programs, particularly those emphasizing emotional and psychological well-being, have a profound impact on stress reduction.

Self-Determination Theory posits that when students have little control over their learning environment or feel constrained by excessive rules and expectations, they become more vulnerable to stress (Deci & Ryan, 2020). Without sufficient opportunities for physical activity, self-expression, and peer collaboration, their ability to manage academic and personal challenges may weaken. In support of this, Research indicates that regular physical activity not only supports students' capacity for emotion regulation and psychological resilience but also contributes to social competence and adaptive

coping skills, attributes that are vital for managing stress effectively (Physical activity and resilience: effects on emotion regulation and psychosocial outcomes, 2022

Moreover, while numerous studies point to the mental health benefits of general physical activity (Biddle & Asare, 2020), there remains a gap in understanding how structured PE classes compare with other forms of exercise. Unlike extracurricular sports or independent workouts, PE classes are built into the school schedule, led by trained instructors, and designed to include a range of activities (Hagger et al., 2021). These features may give PE a distinct advantage in fostering a sense of routine, building social connections, and developing long-term coping skills. In terms of social interaction, students valued Physical Education classes as opportunities to collaborate, communicate, and build strong relationships with peers. This aligns with the study of Smith & Lunstad (2021). Physical Education fosters social networks that are crucial for reducing feelings of isolation and promoting psychological well-being. Group activities and team-based exercises were particularly appreciated for strengthening social bonds and enhancing interpersonal skills. Keegan et al. (2021)

Furthermore, environmental and institutional factors, such as curriculum design, teacher approach, and facility quality, can shape students' perceptions of PE in relation to stress management. Schools that prioritize inclusivity, enjoyment, and skill development tend to foster more positive attitudes toward physical activity, thereby enhancing its stress-reducing potential (McKenzie, 2020). On the other hand, programs that emphasize competition or lack adequate resources may discourage participation and limit the mental health benefits that PE could provide.

Given these considerations, this study examines the perceived benefits of participation in PE classes for students' stress-coping strategies. By addressing the gaps, this research aims to contribute to the development of more effective, student-centered PE programs that support physical health, psychological well-being, Social Interactions, and Academic Performance. Insights from this study may help educators and policymakers refine PE curricula to promote students' holistic development better.

Research Questions

1. What are the perceived benefits of participation in physical education in terms of:
 - 1.1 Physical well-being?
 - 1.2 Mental health?
 - 1.3 Social Interactions?
 - 1.4 Academic performance?
2. What is the stress level of the students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived benefits of Participation I in Physical Education Classes and Students' Stress Level?
4. What measures can be proposed to enhance the university's PE environment in supporting stress reduction and student well-being?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at the University of La Salette, specifically among college students enrolled in the Physical Activity Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT 2) course. This general education course was offered exclusively to eight (8) departments: the College of Accountancy (COA), College of Arts and Sciences (CAS), College of Teacher Education (CTE), College of Engineering and Architecture (CEA), College of Business Education (CBE), College of Information Technology (CIT), College of Medicine and Allied Medical Programs (CMAMP), and College of Nursing Public Health and Midwifery (CONPHM). These departments served as the primary academic departments from which participants in the study were drawn.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Method

The total population comprised 1,371 students enrolled in PATHFIT 2 during the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year. The researcher employed stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation across departments. This sampling method involves dividing the population into subgroups (strata) by departmental affiliation and then randomly selecting respondents from each stratum. To determine the appropriate sample size, the researcher used Raosoft's sample size calculator with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level, yielding a sample size of 301 students.

Departments	Number of Students	Participants
College of Arts and Sciences	80	18
College of Business Education	235	52
College of Teacher Education	43	9
College of Information Technology	60	13
College of Medicine and Allied Medical Program	245	54
College of Nursing, Public Health and Midwifery	339	74
College of Engineering and Architecture	380	61
College of Accountancy	89	20
Total	1,371	301

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher adhered to the necessary ethical and institutional research protocols, and data collection commenced with securing formal approval from the University President to conduct the study. Data were collected via an online survey using Google Forms. The researcher coordinated with the PATHFIT 2 University Instructors to assist in disseminating the research instrument. The instructors were asked to send the Google Forms link to their official group chats. Before answering the questionnaire,

participants were provided with an informed consent letter outlining the purpose of the study, their rights, and the voluntary nature of their participation.

As data collection was conducted online, responses were automatically recorded through Google Forms. Once the required number of responses, based on the calculated sample sizes, was reached, the raw data were exported to Microsoft Excel. Data were coded to facilitate systematic analysis of the responses.

Research Instrument

To collect data for this study, the researcher administered a survey. The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts.

The first part collected the perceived benefits of Physical education for students' physical well-being, Mental health, Social Interactions, and Academic performance. The questionnaire was initially developed by Francis Thaise A. Cineme in 2020 and was adopted from her study titled Physical Education and Stress: A Person-Environment Fit Perspective. This instrument was pilot-tested with 30 students who were not included in the study to assess whether the study's intended objectives were achieved. The questionnaire comprises 14 items assessing the perceived benefits of Physical education for students' physical, Mental, Social, and academic well-being.

The second part is the Perceived Stress Level Scale (PSS), developed by Sheldon Cohen (Cohen et al., 1994; Cohen, 1986), which is commonly used to assess perceived stress.

The test's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.888, indicating high internal consistency.

Data Analysis

The data analysis in this research was conducted using a series of statistical tools:

Mean was used to determine the perceived benefits of physical education in the Physical Well-being, mental health, social interactions, and academic performance of the students.

A 4-Point Scale was used to analyze the interpretation of the perceived benefits of Physical Education.

Number	Range	Description	Interpretation	Rubrics
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Beneficial	Indicates that the respondent fully supports the statement or finds the item extremely valuable.

3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree	Beneficial	Indicates that the respondent supports the statement or finds the item valuable, but not to the highest degree.
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Beneficial	Indicates that the respondent does not fully support the statement or finds the item only somewhat beneficial.
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Beneficial	Indicates that the respondent does not support the statement or finds the item not beneficial at all.

Frequency and Percentage were used to determine the stress level of the students. To assess perceived stress, a 3-point scale was used to interpret students' stress levels.

Score	Interpretation
0-13	Low Stress
14-26	Moderate Stress
27-40	High Stress

Spearman's Rho correlation was used to examine the relationship between the perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education Classes and Students' Stress level.

The quantitative analysis and computation were computer-assisted using SPSS.

RESULTS

This section presents the analyzed data concerning the study's research question. Results are organized in tables, followed by corresponding interpretations and statistical analysis.

Part 1. Perceived Benefits of Physical Education.

The perceived benefits of participation in physical education are classified into physical well-being, mental health, social interaction, and academic performance.

1.1 Physical Well-being

Table 1 presents the perceived benefits of participation in Physical Education classes for students' Physical Well-being.

Table 1. Perceived Benefits of Physical Education on Physical Well-being

	Physical Well-being	Mean	Interpretation
1	I like PE because it helps develop personal discipline.	3.34	Highly Beneficial
2	Regular physical activity offered in PE classes is a significant prerequisite to a satisfying life.	3.19	Beneficial
3	I enjoy PE because of the varied physical activities I can participate in, such as		
	3.1 Aerobic exercises	3.19	Beneficial
	3.2 Plyometric drill	3.19	Beneficial
	3.3 Circuit training	2.99	Beneficial
	3.4 Conditioning exercises.	3.22	Beneficial
	3.5 I believe that PE will enrich my life by:		
	3.6 Improving my overall health and wellness.	3.23	Beneficial
4	Controlling my weight through wise food choices.	3.29	Highly Beneficial
5	PE provides situations for the formation of attitudes that make me a better citizen, such as:		
	5.1 Being able to analyze, evaluate, and make intelligent food choices.	3.21	Beneficial
Category Mean		3.21	Beneficial

The data in Table 1 highlight students' positive perceptions of the role of Physical Education (PE) in enhancing their physical well-being. Among the statements, students most strongly agreed that Physical Education helps develop personal discipline, with a mean of 3.34, indicating a highly beneficial effect. This was followed by the belief that PE helps control weight through prudent food choices, with a mean of 3.29, also rated Highly Beneficial. Next was the statement on improving overall health and wellness with a mean of 3.23, interpreted as Beneficial. The statement on conditioning exercises was rated 3.22, while the ability to analyze, evaluate, and make intelligent food choices was rated 3.21; both were rated as Beneficial.

Similarly, aerobic exercises, regular physical activity that leads to a satisfying life, and plyometric drills each received a mean of 3.19, indicating that students see these activities as Beneficial to their physical well-being. The lowest mean, 2.99, was recorded for circuit training, though it still fell under the Beneficial interpretation.

Overall, with a category mean of 3.21, the findings suggest that students perceive Physical Education as beneficial for enhancing their physical well-being. It highlights how PE contributes to building discipline, encouraging healthy habits, and promoting overall fitness among students.

1.2 Mental Health

Table 2 Shows the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education on Students' Mental Health.

Table 2. Perceived Benefits of Physical Education in Mental Health

	Mental Health	Mean	Interpretation
6	PE should remain in the curriculum because of its physical, mental, and emotional contributions, such as:		
	6.1 It makes me laugh.	3.29	Highly Beneficial
	6.2 It lightens my mood.	3.38	Highly Beneficial
	6.3 It provides positive stress.	3.33	Highly Beneficial
7	I believe that PE will enrich my life by		
	7.1 Developing a positive outlook on life.	3.31	Highly Beneficial
	7.2 Reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression.	3.24	Beneficial
8	I like PE because it provides an alternative activity to mental stress.	3.28	Highly Beneficial
9	Most intellectual activities are just as refreshing as physical activities offered in PE courses.	3.27	Highly Beneficial
	Category Mean	3.30	Highly Beneficial

Table 2 shows students' positive perceptions of the role of Physical Education (PE) in enhancing their mental health, as reflected by a high category mean of 3.30, interpreted as Highly Beneficial.

The highest-rated statement, It lightens my mood (M = 3.38), was interpreted as Highly Beneficial. This was followed by "It provides positive stress" (M = 3.33) and "It makes me laugh" (M = 3.29), both rated as Highly Beneficial, underscoring the emotional benefits students experience during PE. Students also recognized that PE helps develop a positive outlook on life (M = 3.31) and serves as a helpful alternative to academic stress (M = 3.28), both interpreted as Highly Beneficial. Similarly, the statement "Most intellectual activities are just as refreshing as physical activities offered in PE courses" received a rating of M = 3.27, indicating that students rated it as Highly Beneficial, suggesting appreciation for the mental rejuvenation PE offers.

Although slightly lower than the overall mean, the statement "PE helps reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression" (M = 3.24) was still rated as Beneficial, indicating that students acknowledge the psychological benefits of participating in PE.

A category mean of 3.30 indicates that students perceive Physical Education as Highly Beneficial to their mental health. The data suggest that PE not only provides enjoyment and emotional relief but also serves as a coping mechanism for academic stress and contributes to a more positive mental outlook.

1.3 Social Interaction

Table 3 Shows the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education on Students' Social Interactions.

Table 3. Perceived Benefits of Physical Education in Social Interactions

	Social Interaction	Mean	Interpretation
10	PE provides situations for the formation of attitudes that make me a better citizen, such as:		
	10.1 I can be with my Friends	3.25	Highly Beneficial
	10.2 Working with a team makes me collaborative.	3.24	Beneficial
	10.3 Being able to communicate scientific ideas about fitness and wellness.	3.33	Highly Beneficial
11	PE classes are venues for social interactions.	3.28	Highly Beneficial
12	I love group activities and exercises offered in PE classes.	3.31	Highly Beneficial
	Category Mean	3.28	Highly Beneficial

Among the statements, the highest-rated was "PE provides situations for the formation of attitudes that make me a better citizen, such as being able to communicate scientific ideas about fitness and wellness," with a mean of 3.33, interpreted as Highly Beneficial. This was followed by "I love group activities and exercises offered in PE classes," with a mean of 3.31, indicating a rating of "Highly Beneficial." The statement "PE classes are venues for social interaction" came next, with a mean of 3.28, likewise Rated Highly Beneficial.

Meanwhile, "I can be with my friends," which received a mean of 3.25, interpreted as Highly Beneficial; working with a friend garnered the lowest mean of 3.24, interpreted as Beneficial.

Overall, the category mean of 3.28 indicates that students perceive Physical Education as highly beneficial for enhancing social interaction. The results highlight that PE provides a meaningful avenue for students to build friendships, develop teamwork,

and strengthen communication and cooperation, all of which contribute positively to their social development and sense of community.

1.4 Academic Performance

Table 4 Shows the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education on Students' Academic Performance.

Table 4. Perceived Benefits of Physical Education in Academic Performance

Academic Performance	Mean	Interpretation
13 I believe that the PE subject provides learning opportunities.	3.33	Highly Beneficial
14 I believe that PE improves my attentiveness in academic classes.	3.23	Beneficial
Category Mean	3.28	Highly Beneficial

Table 4 shows the students' positive perceptions of the role of Physical Education in enhancing their Academic Performance. Reflected by a category mean of 3.28, interpreted as Highly Beneficial. The highest-rated statement: "I believed that PE subject provides learning opportunities" (M=3.33), interpreted as "Highly Beneficial." Similarly, the statement "I feel that PE helps improve my attentiveness in academic classes" (M=3.23) was interpreted as Beneficial.

Overall, the category mean of 3.28 concludes that students find Physical Education Highly Beneficial in supporting their academic performance. The findings suggest that PE not only promotes physical well-being but also enhances learning opportunities, concentration, and overall academic engagement.

1.5 Summary Table

Table 5 presents the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education across four key categories: Physical Well-being, Mental Health, Social Interactions, and academic performance.

Table 5. Summary of the Perceived Benefits of Physical Education

Category	Mean	Interpretation
1 Physical Well-being	3.21	Beneficial
2 Mental Health	3.30	Highly Beneficial
3 Social Interactions	3.28	Highly Beneficial
4 Academic Performance	3.28	Highly Beneficial
Overall Mean	3.27	Highly Beneficial

Table 5 presents a summary of the perceived benefits of Physical Education (PE) across four key categories: physical well-being, mental health, social interaction, and academic performance. Among these, mental health received the highest mean score (M

= 3.30), indicating a rating of Highly Beneficial, suggesting that students view PE as a significant contributor to emotional well-being and stress relief. This is followed closely by social interaction (M = 3.28) and academic performance (M = 3.28), both interpreted as Highly Beneficial. These findings suggest that students recognize PE as a valuable avenue for building social relationships and enhancing academic focus. In comparison, physical well-being received a slightly lower mean score (M = 3.21), interpreted as Beneficial, indicating that while students appreciate the physical health benefits of PE, they perceive the mental, social, and academic aspects as slightly more impactful.

Overall, the results indicate that students perceive Physical Education as highly beneficial, with a mean of 3.27 as a component of their school experience, particularly in supporting mental health and promoting positive social and academic outcomes.

Part 2. The Stress Level of the Student

Table 6. Overall Distribution of the Students according to their Level of Stress

Category	f	%
High	248	82.4
Moderate	44	14.6
Low	9	3.0

The data show that 248 (82.4%) students fall within the High Stress category, indicating that a large proportion of the student population experiences significant stress.

Meanwhile, 44 (14.6%) of the students are classified as experiencing Moderate Stress, suggesting that only a small segment of students are experiencing a manageable or average level of stress.

Only 9 (3.0%) of the students are in the Low Stress category, highlighting that very few students are not significantly affected by stress.

Part 3. Test of Relationship between the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education classes and Students' Stress Level.

Table 7. Relationship Between the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education Classes and Students' Stress Level

Variables		Stress Level
Physical Well-Being	r	0.109
	p-value	0.059
Mental Health	r	0.154
	p-value	0.008
Social Interactions	r	0.106
	p-value	0.066
Academic Performance	r	0.109

A Spearman's Rho correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between perceived benefits of Participation in Physical Education Classes and Students' stress levels. The test results revealed a weak positive relationship between perceived mental health benefits of Participation in physical education classes and Students' Stress Levels ($r = 0.154$, $p = 0.008$). The other variables are unrelated to one another. Thus, the null hypothesis must be rejected at a 0.05 significance level.

Part 4. Proposed Measures to Promote the Perceived Benefits of Physical Education and to Enhance Physical Education Classes as a Strategy for Stress Reduction to Lessen Students' Stress Levels.

Title: Move for a Change

Program Rationale

The increasing prevalence of high stress levels among students, as reflected in the data where 82.4% of the respondents fall under the High Stress category, presents an urgent call for actionable interventions within the school environment. While stress is an inevitable part of student life, excessive and unmanaged stress can negatively affect students' academic performance, emotional well-being, social interactions, and overall health.

On the other hand, the study's findings clearly indicate that students perceive Physical Education (PE) as a highly beneficial tool for alleviating stress, particularly for enhancing mental health ($M = 3.30$), promoting social interaction ($M = 3.28$), and supporting academic performance ($M = 3.28$). PE activities have been recognized not only for fostering physical fitness but also for nurturing personal discipline, emotional resilience, social connectedness, and cognitive focus. Despite these perceived benefits, PE is often regarded as merely a curricular requirement rather than a strategic mental health intervention. Given the significant relationship between PE's mental health benefits and students' stress levels ($r = 0.154$, $p = 0.008$), it is evident that intentionally integrating PE-driven stress-reduction strategies into the school's daily routines can substantially help reduce students' stress.

This proposed Program, "MOVE FOR A CHANGE: Physical Education for Stress Management Program, aims to capitalize on these positive perceptions and turn them into practical, sustainable activities that are low-cost, student-centered, and feasible within the school's current capacity. By embedding physical activity into everyday school life and promoting the holistic benefits of PE, the program aims to normalize movement as a coping mechanism, reduce stress levels, and cultivate a culture of wellness and active living among students.

Objective	Components	Key Activities or Strategies	Resources and Budget	Success Indicators	Timeline
1. Reduce high-stress-level students within 6 months.	1. PE & Mental Health Awareness Drive 4. Wellness Zones (quiet corners)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness Campaign (posters, videos, FB posts) Setup of Wellness Zones Student Testimonials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Posters (20 pcs) - PHP 600 Yoga Mats (15 pcs) - PHP 3000 Contingency Fund - PHP 4000 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stress level reduction (Pre/Post Survey) Positive feedback on PE (80%) 	Month 1: Orientation, posters Month 3: First impact survey Month 5: Student Testimonials Month 6: Final assessment
2. Ensure at least 60% of students participate in at least 1 PE-driven stress relief activity monthly.	2. Active Breaks 3. Peer-led Fitness Groups 5. Wellness and Fitness Challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 Minute Move Peer Led Fitness Circles Monthly Wellness Challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bluetooth Speakers (2) - PHP 4000 Incentives (medals, certs) - PHP 5000 Contingency Fund - PHP 4000 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 95% monthly participation Regular use of the wellness zone 	Month 2: Start of Active Breaks, 1st Challenge Month 3-5: Continuation & Challenges Month 6: Culminating Activity
3. Institutionalize Active Breaks as part of class routines.	2. Active Breaks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 Minute Move integrated before classes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No additional cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Active breaks in 80% of classes Observation and instructor feedback 	Month 2: Start of Active Breaks Month 4: Midterm Evaluation
4. Strengthen positive perceptions of PE in mental health, social bonding, and academic focus.	1. Awareness Drive 3. Peer Fitness Groups 5. Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness Campaign Fitness Circles Wellness Challenges & Testimonials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All relevant items above (posters, speakers, incentives) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 80% positive perception Participation in testimonials & reflections 	Month 1-5: Ongoing campaigns and challenges Month 6: Report Presentation

DISCUSSION

This study examined the perceived benefits of Physical Education (PE) for students' physical well-being, mental health, social interactions, and academic performance, and assessed their stress levels. Moreover, there is a significant relationship between the perceived benefits of participation in physical education classes and students' stress levels. Moreover, the proposed measure aims to enhance the Benefits of Physical Education and reduce students' stress.

I. Perceived Benefits of Physical Education in Physical Well-being, Mental Health, Social Interactions, and Academic Performance of the Students

The study revealed that students perceived participation in Physical Education Classes as significantly beneficial across multiple domains. While all four aspects: Physical Well-being, Mental Health, Social Interactions, and Academic Performance were acknowledged, students placed the most significant emphasis on the mental health, social, and academic benefits of Physical Education.

Students reported that Physical Education Activities are perceived as uplifting their mood, providing emotional release, and serving as a positive coping mechanism for academic pressure. This perception is consistent with studies by McKenzie (2021) and Liu et al. (2025), who highlighted that participation in physical activities fosters emotional resilience, enhances mood, and mitigates negative emotions among students. The students' recognition of the emotional benefits of Physical Education supports the theory that PE can play a vital role in managing stress.

In terms of social interaction, students valued Physical Education classes as opportunities to collaborate, communicate, and build strong relationships with peers. This aligns with the study of Smith & Lunstad (2021) and Keegan et al. (2021), who emphasized that Physical Education fosters social networks that are crucial for reducing feelings of isolation and promoting psychological well-being. Group activities and team-based exercises were particularly appreciated for strengthening social bonds and enhancing interpersonal skills.

Regarding students' academic performance, Physical Education is perceived to contribute to improved focus, attentiveness, and learning engagement. These findings are supported by Teuber et al. (2024), who documented that physical activity positively affects cognitive functions such as memory, concentration, decision-making, and critical thinking. The belief that PE enhances academic focus further validates the cognitive benefits of incorporating movement into daily routines.

Interestingly, while physical well-being remains an essential benefit of PE, students seemed to prioritize the mental and social dimensions over traditional fitness-related outcomes. This perception indicates that Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education Classes are not merely viewed as a means to Physical Health, but as a Comprehensive wellness activity that supports the Emotions, Cognitive, and Social Development of the students.

II. The Stress Level of the Students

The findings reveal that most students report high levels of stress, with only a few reporting low levels. This aligns with the study by Alzahrani et al. (2023), who found that academic demands, time pressure, and performance anxiety are major contributors to student stress. Their study emphasized that prolonged academic stress can adversely affect students' mental well-being and academic performance, echoing the present study's finding that stress is a widespread concern.

Moreover, Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2020) posits that when students have little control over their learning environment or feel constrained by excessive rules and expectations, they become more vulnerable to stress. Without sufficient opportunities for physical activity, self-expression, and peer collaboration, their ability to manage academic and personal challenges may weaken. In support of this, Research indicates that regular physical activity not only supports students' capacity for emotion regulation and psychological resilience but also contributes to social competence and adaptive coping skills, attributes that are vital for managing stress effectively (Physical activity and resilience: effects on emotion regulation and psychosocial outcomes, 2022).

Several studies further reinforce this idea. Smith (2021) indicates that physical activity is associated with positive emotions and well-being among students, suggesting meaningful psychological benefits. Likewise, Rodríguez-Bravo et al., 2020 stated that, engaging in structured physical activity and cooperative sports has been shown to enhance students' emotional stability, self-confidence, and overall psychological well-being, providing a protective effect against the negative impact of stress.

III. Significant Relationship on the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education Classes and Student's Stress level

The findings revealed a significant relationship between mental health benefits and stress level, supporting existing literature emphasizing the psychological value of physical education. Recent studies have shown that participation in PE and physical activity contributes to improved mental health by enhancing emotional regulation, resilience, and coping abilities among students (Han et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2024). Physical activity has been consistently linked to better psychological well-being, which may influence how students perceive and manage stress in academic settings (Rodríguez-Bravo et al., 2020).

These findings highlighted the central role of mental health- focused PE activities in addressing student stress. It supports the findings of Dinas et al. (2020) and Lee & Kim (2021) that structured PE programs, particularly those emphasizing emotional and psychological well-being, have a profound impact on stress reduction.

The lack of a significant relationship in other domains, such as physical fitness and social benefits, indicates that although these aspects are important, they do not directly influence students' perceived stress-coping abilities. This indicates that Physical Education must place greater emphasis on emotional wellness activities, such as

mindfulness techniques and mood-enhancing exercises, to maximize their stress-relieving potential.

These findings highlight the need for Physical Education programs to integrate mental health-focused and collaborative activities, such as mindfulness practices, relaxation techniques, and mood-enhancing exercises. PE teachers should design activities that not only improve physical skills but also nurture emotional resilience, peer support, and self-awareness. By placing greater emphasis on emotional wellness in PE, schools can adopt a more holistic approach that helps students manage stress effectively and foster overall well-being.

IV. Proposed Measure

The proposed program, MOVE FOR A CHANGE Physical Education for Stress Management Program, was developed in response to the study's finding that majority of students experience high stress levels. While stress is a normal part of student life, unmanaged stress can affect academic performance, emotional health, and social relationships.

Results showed that students view Physical Education as highly beneficial, particularly in improving mental health, enhancing social interaction, and supporting academic performance. A significant relationship was also found between PE's mental health benefits and students' stress levels, suggesting that PE can serve as an effective strategy for stress reduction.

The "MOVE FOR A CHANGE" program transforms these findings into practical and low-cost interventions that promote movement and wellness. Key components such as Active Breaks, Peer-Led Fitness Groups, Wellness Zones, and Awareness Campaigns encourage collaboration, mindfulness, and regular physical activity. These initiatives align with studies by Eime et al. (2020), Lubans et al. (2022), and Deci and Ryan (2020), which emphasize that physical and social engagement enhances emotional regulation, resilience, and motivation.

Overall, this program positions Physical Education as more than a curricular requirement it becomes a holistic approach to student well-being. By integrating active, collaborative, and wellness-focused activities into daily school routines, PE can effectively reduce stress, strengthen mental health, and foster a culture of active living among students.

Conclusions

The study assessed the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education Classes in Physical Well-being, social interactions, and Academic Performance of the students. Moreover the Stress Level of the students and the Significant Relationships. The findings revealed these insights:

Students perceived Physical Education classes as highly beneficial across multiple dimensions, most notably in mental health, social interactions and academic performance. Physical Education is viewed not only as a means of enhancing physical fitness but also as an avenue for emotional relief, social connection, and improved focus on the academic life of the students. Mental benefits such as mood improvement and stress alleviation stood out as the most valued aspect, followed closely by opportunities for social bonding and cognitive engagement. While Physical Well-being was also perceived as beneficial, it appeared to be less emphasized compared to social advantages.

A substantial portion of the student population is experiencing a high level of stress, indicating a pressing concern for students' mental health and well-being. Despite recognizing the benefits of PE, these stress levels remain significantly elevated, suggesting that current stress management strategies within the institution are not enough to lessen the stress level of the student.

The study identified a significant relationship between the perceived mental health benefits of Physical Education and Students' Stress Levels. This indicates the students who recognize PE's weak positive impact on their mental health are more likely to cope better with stress. However perceived benefits in physical well-being, social interactions, and academic performance did not show a significant relationship with stress levels, suggesting that mental health is primary domain through which PE contributes to stress coping.

The study concludes that Physical Education (PE) plays a vital role in promoting student well-being and managing stress. Respondents identified as experiencing high stress levels, the findings highlight the urgent need. In response, the proposed "MOVE FOR A CHANGE: Physical Education for Stress Management Program" serves as a practical and sustainable framework that integrates Active Breaks, Peer-Led Fitness Groups, Wellness Zones, and Awareness Campaigns into school routines. These initiatives promote collaboration, mindfulness, and regular physical activity key factors in building emotional resilience and reducing stress.

Recommendations

To address the identified gap, the following recommendations are proposed to promote the perceived benefits of Physical Education and to enhance PE classes as a strategy for reducing student stress.

1. To Enhance the Perceived Benefits of Participation in Physical Education Classes:
 - 1.1 Integrate mental health-focused activities such as mindfulness and relaxation exercises. Into PE classes to capitalize on their perceived psychological benefits
 - 1.2 Reinforce the academic relevance of Physical Education by aligning physical activities with cognitive development exercises, enhancing attentiveness and concentration in students.

- 1.3 Conduct awareness campaigns to further inform students about the holistic benefits of PE in fostering overall well-being beyond physical fitness.
2. To Lessen the Stress Level of the Students:
 - 2.1 Implement the “MOVE FOR A CHANGE” program, which focuses on integrating PE-based stress relief activities into daily school routines.
 - 2.2 Establish Active Breaks within academic classes to help students manage their academic fatigue and stress in real time.
 - 2.3 Utilize the Wellness Zone within the Physical Education laboratory, where students can engage in mindfulness, stretching, or quiet reflection during free time.
 - 2.4 Conduct regular mental health and stress level assessments to monitor student well-being and provide timely interventions.
3. The significant relationship between the Perceived Participation in Physical Education Classes and the Stress level of the students suggests that:
 - 3.1 Reposition PE classes as a mental health intervention, emphasizing emotional well-being as a core outcome.
 - 3.2 Train PE instructors to incorporate stress management techniques such as breathing exercises, mood boosters, and reflective activities into their lesson plans.
 - 3.3 Align Initiatives with counseling and guidance programs, creating a collaborative approach between physical activities and mental health services.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The entire research process will be embedded with ethical considerations to protect the rights and well-being of the participants. In the course of this study, informed consent will be sought from each participant when necessary, and prior to their participation, to ensure that their rights, including the purpose of the study, voluntary participation, and confidentiality, are addressed. Reassurance will also be provided to all participants that their responses will remain anonymous and will be used solely for this research. In addition, the study will obtain approval from the ethics review board of the University of La Salette, in accordance with the institution's policy on conducting research involving human subjects. This ethical framework will protect the participants under study, enhance transparency, and ensure that the research is conducted with integrity.

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REFERENCES

- Alzahrani, A., Bashatah, A., Alshehri, M., & Almalki, M. (2023). The impact of academic stress on the mental health of university students: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Affective Disorders Reports*, 11, 100518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadr.2023.100518>
- American Psychological Association. (2020). *Stress in America™ 2020: A national mental health crisis*. Retrieved from <https://www.apa.org/news/press/releases/stress/2020/report>
- An, J. (2025). Physical education, intrinsic motivation, and academic stress among Filipino senior high school students. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 8(7), 1952–1961. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v8-i7-70>
- Bailey, R. (2020). Physical education and sport in schools: A review of benefits and outcomes. *Journal of School Health*, 78(8), 473–481. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1746-1561.2008.00327.x>
- Biddle, S. J. H., & Asare, M. (2023). Physical activity and mental health in children and adolescents: A review of reviews. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 57(4), 178–185. Retrieved from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21807669/>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2020). *Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness*. Guilford Press. retrieved from <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2017-04680-000>
- Dinas, P. C., Koutedakis, Y., & Nevill, A. M. (2020). Physical activity and its impact on mental health: A review. *Psychological Bulletin*, 146(6), 521–545.
- Dishman, R. K., McDowell, C. P., & Herring, M. P. (2021). Physical activity and mental health: Evidence for stress-buffering effects in young adults. *Psychosomatic Medicine*, 83(4), 330–340.
- Han, X., Li, H., & Zhang, Y. (2025). Physical activity enhances college students' mental health through social adaptability and exercise behavior. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, Article 1457165. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1457165>
- Hagger, M. S., Cameron, L. D., Hamilton, K., Hankonen, N., & Lintunen, T. (Eds.). (2020). *The handbook of behavior change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Keegan, R. J., & MacPhail, A. (2021). Physical education, social interaction, and psychological well-being: A review of evidence. *International Journal of Physical Education & Sports Sciences*, 15(2), 45–62. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351070467_Motivational_Climate_Measures_in_Sport_A_Systematic_Review
- Kim, J., & McKenzie, L. A. (2021). The effects of physical exercise on stress-coping and well-being among university students in the context of leisure. *Health*, 6(19), 2570–2580.

- Lee, E. J., & Kim, J. (2021). Effects of physical activity on the mental health of university students: A systematic review. *Health Education Research*, 36(3), 277–292. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyab008>
- Liu, Y., Zhang, X., & Chen, W. (2025). How does physical education influence university students' psychological health? An analysis from the dual perspectives of social support and exercise behavior, 16, 1457165. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1457165>
- McKenzie, T. L. (2020). Assessing school physical education and physical activity programs: Selected tools. In R. Carson & C. Webster (Eds.), *Comprehensive school physical activity programs: Putting research into evidence-based practice* (pp. 247–260). Human Kinetics.
- Physical activity and resilience among college students: The mediating effects of basic psychological needs. (2022). *Journal of Behavioral Health*, 13(4), 112–128. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/7/3722>
- Reigal, R. E., Moral-Campillo, L., Juárez-Ruiz de Mier, R., Morillo-Baro, J. P., Morales-Sánchez, V., Pastrana, J. L., & Hernández-Mendo, A. (2020). Physical fitness is associated with attention and concentration in adolescents. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, Article 110. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00110>
- Rodríguez-Bravo, A. E., De-Juanas, Á., & García-Castilla, F. J. (2020). Effect of physical-sports leisure activities on young people's psychological wellbeing. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 543951. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.543951>
- Smith, T. W., & Holt-Lunstad, J. (2021). The effects of team sports participation on mental health: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 147(6), 578–602. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000303>
- Teuber, Z., Bock, C., Faas, S., & Woll, A. (2024). Daily leisure-time physical activity and active study breaks reduce stress and improve academic performance indicators in university students: A longitudinal study. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 1205. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-18082-z>